

SiC_w REINFORCED Al-Cu-Mg-Li ALLOYS

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ABSTRACT

Additions of SiC_w and lithium have both been shown by prior investigators to increase the elastic modulus of aluminum alloys. The present investigation has examined the potential for combining these beneficial effects in a dilute Al-Cu-Mg-Li matrix reinforced with 5-10 volume pct SiC_w. Both the elastic modulus and the tensile yield strength of SiC_w reinforced Al-Cu-Mg can be enhanced thru the addition of 1 wt. pct Li. However, the tensile ductility of the Li containing composite was somewhat less than that currently achievable in more heavily deformed SiC_w reinforced Al-Cu-Mg sheet. Future matrix and process development procedures are outlined that offer the potential for attaining higher strengths and ductilities in SiC_w reinforced Al-Cu-Mg-Li metal matrix composites.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Matrix, aluminum; Silicon carbide; Whisker composite; Mechanical behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION

Replacement of conventional aerospace aluminum alloys with advanced alloys and composites is of world-wide technological interest. For example, the incorporation of Li in Al-Cu-Mg alloys has been shown to result in an increase in the structural efficiency of aluminum alloys (1). An alternative path has been the development of discontinuously reinforced Al-Cu-Mg metal matrix composites (2).

While both these developments offer the potential for enhanced structural performance, an interesting issue that remains largely unexplored involves the possible synergistic effects that might be possible thru the incorporation of a discontinuous reinforcement in an appropriate Al-Cu-Mg-Li matrix. Webster's earlier study of liquid phase processed SiC_w reinforced Al-Li and Al-Cu-Mg-Li composites (3), while suggesting the potential that might be achieved with these systems, examined composites which generally failed prior to attaining the 0.2 pct yield

strength. In contrast, White et al. (4) have demonstrated that satisfactory SiC particulate reinforced Al-1Cu-0.5Mg-2.23Li matrix composites can be fabricated utilizing a direct spray technique. The study reported herein was designed to continue this assessment of the potential benefits in mechanical performance that might be gained thru the inclusion of rather low volume fraction, 5-10 volume pct., SiC_w in a lean Al-Cu-Mg-Li matrix. A companion investigation of the age hardening response of these discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites has been presented elsewhere (5).

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The chemical composition of the SiC_w reinforced Al-Mg-Cu-Li alloy examined in this study is shown in Table 1. Selection of this alloy content was designed to simplify microstructural examination and was based upon prior studies of precipitation hardening in Al-Cu-Mg-Li alloys. The matrix precipitates observed after aging Al-Cu-Mg alloys containing 2-3 weight pct. Li at 190°C include spherical metastable δ', based on Al₃Li(Li₃-type), S(Al₂CuMg) and T₁(Al₂CuLi), the latter being promoted at higher Cu contents (6,7). The lean alloy content utilized in this study resulted in co-precipitation of δ' and S (5).

TABLE 1. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION

SiC _w Nominal	SiC _w vol %	Li wt %	Cu wt %	Mg wt %	Fe wt %	Mn wt %	Density g/cm ³
5	6.4	0.88	1.04	0.69	0.040	0.011	2.635
10	11.1	0.82	0.89	0.71	0.038	0.014	2.645

Details of the SiC_w reinforced powder composite fabrication have been given previously (8). Briefly the composites were fabricated as 130 mm diameter billets by blending helium gas atomized powders with grade F-8 silicon carbide whiskers, cold compacting, and vacuum hot pressing in the mushy, liquid-solid zone. Utilization of the higher purity F-8 SiC_w and pressing just above the alloy solidus was designed to eliminate the large Al-Li and SiO₂/SiC particulates that had previously been shown to limit the tensile ductility of these and other SiC_w reinforced Al composites (3,9). Following compaction the billets were hot extruded to 12.7 mm thick by 127 mm wide planks, an 11.8 to 1 reduction ratio, cut in 200 mm lengths and hot cross-rolled to 2 mm sheet.

Mechanical property characterization of the Al-Cu-Mg-Li composites included dynamic moduli and tensile measurements. The former utilized a 1.5 mm square by 25 mm length specimen, its length lying parallel to the final rolling direction, and involved determination of the thru transmission velocity with subsequent conversion by standard procedures to Young's modulus (10). Tensile testing again utilized samples with their tensile axis coincident with the final rolling direction, testing being carried out at an initial strain rate of $7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ on an Instron Model 1125 with an Instron 25 mm gage extensometer.

Six (6) heat treatment conditions were examined. These heat treatment conditions, Table 2, were selected following initial studies of the natural and artificial aging response of these composites (5). They were chosen to represent underaged, peakaged (maximum hardness) and overaged conditions as determined from Rockwell B hardness measurements, Figure 1.

TABLE 2. TENSILE AGING TREATMENTS*

Aging Temp °C	Aging Times - Hours		
	100	1.0	16
200	0.5	32	256

*Solution treatment: 525°C, 30 min., CWQ

3. RESULTS

Optical microscopy revealed that the hot rolled composite sheet was 2-D isotropic, that is the SiC_w reinforcements, while randomly oriented within the plane of the sheet, were aligned with respect to the thru thickness sheet direction. Moreover some degree of SiC_w banding was observed, the degree of this nonuniformity decreasing with increasing SiC_w content.

Ultrasonic moduli measurements, Table 3, indicated that there was a slight but discernable influence of thermal processing on the stiffness of the Al-Cu-Mg-Li composites examined in this study. This effect paralleled the age hardening response of the matrices, compare Table 3 and Figure 1, and can be ascribed to continued δ' precipitation and coarsening (5,12). A more pronounced effect of SiC_w content on the Young's modulus was observed. Increasing the SiC_w content resulted in an increase in modulus, independent of thermal treatment, the difference between the 5 volume pct and 10 volume pct SiC_w reinforced composite averaging 11.1 GPa.

TABLE 3. MODULUS OF ELASTICITY

Aging Temp °C	Aging Time hrs.	Young's Modulus (GPa)	
		SiC _w Content (vol. pct)	
		5	10
100	1	90.3	102.0
	16	91.7	101.3
	512	92.4	104.8
200	0.5	91.7	102.7
	32	92.4	104.1
	256	90.3	100.6

Representative tensile stress-strain curves for SiC_w composites are shown in Figure 2. Serrated yielding was observed for both composites in the underaged conditions, those having been aged for 1 and 16 hrs at 100°C, and 0.5 hrs at 200°C. The extent of this repeated yielding phenomena appeared to be independent of the SiC_w content, although the stress amplitude and the strain for the first observable onset of serrated yielding were functions of thermal processing. For

FIGURE 1. Aging response of Al-Cu-Mg-Li composites aged at (a) 100°C and (b) 200°C.

FIGURE 2. Representative stress-strain curves for 10 vol. pct reinforced Al-Cu-Mg-Li composite aged for (a) 1 hr and (b) 512 hrs at 100°C.

example, the onset strain tended to increase with increasing aging time at 100°C, while the stress amplitude after aging for 0.5 hr at 200°C appeared to be larger than that observed following aging at 100°C. Detailed study also indicated that the stress changes associated with these serrations were not uniform, a hardening increment being associated with each.

Finally, serrated yielding was not observed when S precipitation occurred, that is after aging 512 hrs at 100°C or 32 and 256 hrs at 200°C. While studies of serrated yielding continue, these observations are consistent with those reported by Wert and Wycliffe, (12), serrated yielding in Al-Cu-Mg-Li alloys being ascribed to Cu/Mg in solid solutions.

The tensile yield and ultimate strengths as well as the tensile strain to failure were also functions of the aging temperature and times, Figures 3 and 4. The response of the tensile yield and ultimate strengths to aging temperature and time, independent of SiC_w content, again paralleled that of the hardness measurements, increasing with aging time at 100°C and going thru a maxima upon aging at 200°C. These changes were mirrored by those of the tensile strain to failure, the latter decreasing with increasing aging time at 100°C and going thru a minima upon aging at 200°C. In all instances higher levels of tensile yield and ultimate strength and lower tensile strains to failure were observed in the 10 volume pct composite.

Macroscopically, the tensile specimens all appeared to fracture thru the sheet thickness along planes of maximum shear. While the appearance of this shear failure was independent of SiC_w content, the details of its progression was a function of thermal treatment. In underaged specimens, 0.5 hrs at 200°C, 1 hr and 16 hrs at 100°C, failure occurred along a single macroscopic shear plane. In contrast, after peak or overaging, 32 and 256 hrs at 200°C, and 512 hrs at 100°C, fracture appeared to have occurred in a step-wise fashion and was associated with several shear planes.

Scanning electron microscopy indicated that failure was not associated with the presence of large inclusions. Rather microscopic analysis of these fracture surfaces showed the presence of dimples associated with either individual whiskers or fine particles. Qualitatively this microscopic failure mode appeared to be dependent on both SiC_w content and thermal history, the dimple size tending to decrease with increasing aging time and decreasing SiC_w content.

4. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Comparison of this study with that of Webster (3) shows that elimination of large SiC, SiO₂ and Al-Li inclusions thru proper selection of reinforcement purity and hot pressing conditions can result in the production of a SiC_w reinforced Al-Cu-Mg-Li composite having an attractive combination of mechanical properties. For example, Table 4 shows that the tensile yield strength and elastic modulus of the 10 volume pct SiC_w reinforced Al-Cu-Mg-Li alloy examined in this study exceeded that reported for a 10 volume pct SiC_w reinforced Al-Cu-Mg (2009) composite.

FIGURE 3: Influence of aging time on tensile properties of 5 vol. pct SiC_w reinforced Al-Cu-Mg-Li composite aged at (a) 100°C and (b) 200°C.

FIGURE 4: Influence of aging time on tensile properties of 10 vol. pct SiC_w reinforced Al-Cu-Mg-Li composite aged at (a) 100°C and (b) 200°C.

Specifically, the expected enhancement of the elastic moduli originally sought thru the addition of Li to a SiC_w reinforced Al-Cu-Mg composite has been demonstrated. At 10 volume pct SiC_w reinforcement the Young's modulus of 2009 is 97.9 GPa, while the lean Li alloy composition utilized in this study achieved moduli in excess of 104 GPa, a 6.2 pct increase. In addition, the tensile yield strength was increased by 6.8 pct. Further comparison shows that the specific stiffness and strength properties of the Al-Cu-Mg-Li composite generally exceed those of the 2009 matrix composite.

TABLE 4. COMPARISON OF 10 VOL. PCT SiC_w REINFORCED ALUMINUM ALLOY COMPOSITE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Alloy	ρ (g/cm ³)	E (GPa)	E/ ρ (KNm/gm)	σ_y (MPa)	$\frac{\sigma_y}{\rho}$ $\left(\frac{N \cdot m}{gm}\right)$	σ_u (MPa)	$\frac{\sigma_u}{\rho}$ $\left(\frac{N \cdot m}{gm}\right)$	ϵ (pct)	Ref.
2009	2.824	97.2	34.4	337.9	119.7	592.9	210.0	7.5	2
present	2.645	104.8	39.6	360.9	136.4	555.3	209.9	3.0	--

However, the tensile ductility of the Al-Cu-Mg-Li matrix composite is lower than that of the 2009 matrix composites. It should be recognized though that the tensile properties of the 2009 composite were determined from sheet/plate that had undergone a substantially greater amount of thermomechanical working. Several prior investigations of thermomechanical working in SiC_w reinforced 2XXX alloys have shown that tensile ductility is enhanced by increasing amounts of deformation processing (8,13); therefore it is expected that more extensive thermomechanical treatment of the Al-Cu-Mg-Li composites examined in this study should result in enhanced ductility. Furthermore, the thermal processing conditions examined in the current study were quite limited, aging at temperatures between 125° and 175°C appear to be more appropriate (4).

Finally, the matrix chemical composition selected for this study did not result in a substantial age hardening response (5). It appears therefore that matrix composition having slightly higher Cu, Mg and Li concentrations, with appropriate thermomechanical processing, should result in further enhancements in mechanical performance.

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